

PREPARATION, PROPERTY AND APPLICATION OF CNT BUCKYPAPER AND ITS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotube (CNT) has drawn wide attention due to its remarkable mechanical, electrical and thermal properties. In recent years, CNTs powder has achieved mass production. How to make the utmost of its outstanding properties in the macroscopic scale and enable its wide application in practical engineering is a worldwide concern both in research and industry. In this work, we prepared a relatively big CNTs film (buckypaper, BP) with a diameter up to 285 mm through a solution filtration method, enhanced its mechanical properties (especially toughness) by a polymer binder and explored its potential application in tribology and lightning strike protection (LSP) of the carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminate. A thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) elastomer was employed to enhance its mechanical properties. The resultant composites gained simultaneous improvements in stiffness (3.4-fold), failure strength (9.6-fold) and toughness (51-fold) compared to those of the as-prepared BP film. Taking advantage of the “self-lubricating” effect of CNTs, herein we applied the BP to enhance the tribological performance of the epoxy resin. It was found that BP/epoxy composite exhibited superior tribological properties compared to the neat epoxy resin. Moreover, even after subjected to harsh wear, BP/epoxy composite still retained high electrical conductivity due to the robust CNTs network. Based on its outstanding electrical property, we explored the potential of BP in LSP of CFRP laminate. BP-based coatings composed of MWCNTs BP and insulating adhesives of the appropriate thickness were developed to protect the CFRP laminate from lightning strike. It was demonstrated that the conductive BP can facilitate the lightning current to the ground and dissipate the energy. Moreover, a relatively thick insulating adhesive, which outperformed the conductive adhesive, can hinder the transfer of the lightning current through the thickness direction to CFRP laminates, thus further enhance the LSP effectiveness.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, carbon nanotube (CNT) has drawn wide attention due to its remarkable mechanical, electrical and thermal performance. But individual CNT cannot be applied directly in the industry except for micro and nano devices. To make the utmost of its unique mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties in the macroscopic scale, macro-scale architectures of CNTs, such as CNTs fibers, 2D films and 3D foams, have attracted increasingly attention. Buckypaper (BP), as a non-woven film of CNTs, inherits the superior properties of CNTs and is believed to be a good candidate for many applications, such as deicers [1], electrodes [2], actuators [3], sensors [4], organic light-emitting diodes [5], electromagnetic shielding [6] and as reinforcement for polymer composites [7, 8], etc.

BP can be prepared by filtration method [9, 10], CVD method [11-13], layer-by-layer method [14], electrophoretic deposition method [15] and frit compression method [16], etc. Although BP has achieved mass production by a CVD method in Nanocomp Technologies, Inc., it is still a big challenge to obtain a large-scale BP through general methods, especially for the last three methods. Since CNTs powder has achieved mass production, how to enable its wide application in practical engineering is a worldwide concern both in research and industry. So in this work we designed a device to prepare a relatively big BP by filtrate the CNTs solution, which derived from CNTs powder, and explored its potential application.

The mechanical properties of BPs prepared by filtration are relatively weak, resulting in somewhat difficulty in handling them in practice. The modulus and tensile strength of the unmodified BPs reported in literatures usually fall into the range of 0.2-5 GPa and 2-33 MPa [17, 18], respectively, whereas the elongation at break is relatively low and varies from 0.5% to 4%, specifically no more than 15% [19], indicating their brittle nature. To improve the mechanical properties of BPs, researchers have developed many approaches to modify CNTs, such as chemically crosslinking [20, 21], physically aligning [22], or binding by polymer binders [23]. For the latter one, the commonly-used polymer binders are thermosetting resins, such as epoxy and bismaleimide resins. Although the resultant composites show high modulus and strength compared to the neat BP, they also inherit the intrinsic low fracture toughness and brittleness of the thermosetting resins. In some case, the elongation at break of the composites prepared is only 2.5% [8, 24]. Such a remarkable imbalance of the key mechanical properties may limit the applications of BP composites greatly. So far, only few works have focused on the toughness of the BP composites and the related toughening method. So in this work, we tried to use a more ductile polymer, i.e. thermoplastic polyurethane elastomer (TPU) to enhance the mechanical properties of BP, especially its toughness, and unveiled the possible reinforcing mechanisms through in situ Raman spectrums and SEM of the sample fracture surfaces.

CNTs are reported to exhibit wear-reducing effect in polymers owing to their excellent mechanical and thermal performance. It is demonstrated that CNTs can decrease the wear volume and COF of the matrix due to its self-lubricating effect [25-27]. However, the large aspect ratio and huge specific surface area of CNTs will bring about significant thickening effect to polymers (especially for epoxy resin), and thus result in processing difficulty and poor dispersion of the CNTs. The weight fractions of CNTs in epoxy composites are often less than 5% in most cases [28], leading to a limited anti-wear performance and relatively low electrical conductivity (10^{-6} - 10^{-1} S/m, anti-static level) [29]. BP-based polymer composites with loading of CNTs (as high as 20-70 wt %) exhibit ultrahigh tensile strength and Young's modulus, which are comparable to those of the unidirectional carbon-fiber reinforced composites [8, 24]. Moreover, owing to the network structure of CNTs, BP-based polymer composites show much higher electrical conductivity (10^2 - 10^3 S/m) [30]. To the best of our knowledge, so far, studies on tribological behaviors of BP-based composites have not been found in the open literature. Herein, we applied the BP to simultaneously enhance the tribological and electrical properties of epoxy resin. The CNTs were functionalized by a convenient ozone treatment to tailor their interface with the epoxy matrix. The resultant BP/epoxy composites were expected to be applicable in the fields where both excellent wear resistance and high electrical conductivity are required simultaneously, such as the electrical brush in electric motors.

Due to their high specific stiffness and strength, carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) have been increasingly used in aircraft structures to reduce the overall weight and to save fuel. However, their relatively low electrical conductivity leads to the vulnerability to lightning strike [31]. As the commercially utilized lightning strike protection (LSP) system made of metal mesh cannot satisfy the requirement for weight reduction in aircraft [32], herein, based on the lightweight and highly conductive properties of the BP, we explored its potential application in LSP of the CFRP. Generally speaking, a conductive adhesive may be beneficial for LSP by conducting the lightning current to the ground and dissipating energy; while an insulating adhesive may be destroyed by the lightning strike owing to the high resistance and the subsequently high resistive heat. However, there is no related research to demonstrate this issue in the open literature. In this work, BP was bonded onto the surface of the CFRP laminates by three kinds of adhesives with different electrical conductivity to protect the CFRP laminates from lightning strike. The influence of BP and adhesive on the LSP effectiveness was systematically studied through simulated lightning strike tests. According to the experimental results and the finite element simulation, the possible mechanisms for LSP were discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Preparation of the BP

MWCNTs (6-8 nm in diameter, up to 50 μ m in length, and purity >93 wt %, FloTubeTM 7000, CNano Technology Ltd., Beijing, China) were utilized to fabricate BP through a solution filtration

method [33]. Bigger BP films (with a diameter up to ~285 mm), if needed, can be obtained by the same method only using more CNTs dispersion and larger filter equipment (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Home-made device (a) for the preparation of the relatively big BP (b).

2.2 Preparation of BP/TPU composites and characterization of its mechanical properties

TPU (Elastollan 1185A10, MFI value <20, BASF Co.) was dissolved in N, N-dimethylformamide to form solutions of 0.01 wt%. A certain amount of solution was filtered through the BP under vacuum to infiltrate BP. After infiltration, the composite samples were obtained by drying the resin-wetted BP at 60 °C under vacuum for 24 h to eliminate the solvent completely. The amount of TPU solutions was varied to obtain the composite samples containing various TPU fractions. The composite samples are designated as BP/TPU-x, where x indicates the amount of TPU solution. Higher x value indicates larger amount of TPU solution used for infiltration.

A dynamic mechanical analyzer (TA, DMA Q800) was employed to evaluate mechanical properties of the as-prepared BP and their composites. The static tensile tests were conducted in ramp displacement mode with a pre-strain 0.01% and at a ramp rate of 20 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. The integrated area under the tensile curve, representing the energy to break the samples, was used to evaluate their toughness.

2.3 Preparation of the BP/EP composites and characterization of its tribological properties

The BP/epoxy composite samples for the wear tests were prepared as illustrated in Fig. 2. The BP was soaked in a mixture of epoxy resin, curing agent and acetone (weight ratio =37:34:35) at 45 °C for 4 h and thereafter at 65 °C for 4 h under vacuum to be fully infiltrated by the resin (Step 1). The wet BP film was laid on the mould part A (Step 2). Then a certain amount of epoxy-curing agent mixture was further poured onto the top of the wet film (Step 3). The additional epoxy resin served as the sample supporter during wear tests. The composite samples were cured in oven according to the recommended procedure (Step 4). The neat epoxy samples were prepared by the same way. The thickness of the samples is about 4 mm.

Figure 2 A schematic diagram for preparation of the composite samples.

To tailor the interface of the CNTs and polymer matrix, a convenient ozone treatment was utilized to modify the pristine MWCNTs as described in our previous work [34, 35]. And the modified-CNTs

were utilized to prepare BP for further combination with the epoxy resin. For clarity, in the following sections the prefix ‘*p*-’ is used to denote the pristine CNTs and their related BP, BP/epoxy composite samples, and prefix ‘*f*-’ is used to denote the ozone-modified matters. For example, *f*-BP denotes a BP made up of the modified-CNTs.

A universal tribometer (UMT-3, Bruker Corporation) was utilized to evaluate the friction and wear behaviors of the samples under dry sliding condition through a ball-on-disc configuration, as shown in Fig. 3. The wear tests were performed under ambient conditions at different sliding velocities of 20-120 mm/s, various normal loads of 1-6 N, and test duration of 12 h. Volume loss of the specimen, ΔV , was measured by a confocal laser microscope (Olympus 3D LEXT OLS4000) after test using a stitching method. The specific wear rate, W_s , which describes the wear performance under the chosen conditions for a tribosystem, was calculated by

$$W_s = \frac{\Delta V}{F_N L} \quad (1)$$

where F_N is the normal load applied on the steel ball during sliding, L is the total sliding distance. Each result was an average value of at least five repeated tests. More detailed information can be found in Ref.[35].

Figure 3 A schematic diagram for configuration of the ball-on-disc wear test.

2.4 Preparation of BP-coated CFRP laminate samples and the simulated lightning strike tests

The BP was bonded on the surface of the CFRP laminate by three kinds of epoxy-based adhesives with different electrical conductivities, i.e. neat adhesive, conductive adhesive and highly insulating adhesive, to protect the laminate from lightning strike. The neat adhesive was a pure epoxy resin; the conductive adhesive was made of epoxy resin filled by ~ 1.0 wt % CNTs (CNTs/EP); the highly insulating adhesive was composed of epoxy resin with ~ 20 wt % hexagonal boron nitride (BN) and was denoted as BN/EP. The information of the curing agent and the curing procedure can be found in Ref.[36]. The electrical properties of the cured adhesives are listed in Table 1, suggesting that CNTs/EP is the most conductive adhesive with conductivity of about 0.4 S/m while BN/EP exhibits the best insulating properties with breakdown strength of about 185 kV/mm.

Material	Electrical conductivity (S/m)	Breakdown strength in oil (kV/mm)
Pure EP	$\sim 2.3 \times 10^{-8}$	101.5 ± 21.4
CNTs/EP	~ 0.4	2.1 ± 0.2
BN/EP	$\sim 6.8 \times 10^{-12}$	185.9 ± 7.7

Table 1: Electrical properties of the cured adhesives.

The carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates were quasi-isotropic laminates with lay-up sequence $[+45/0/-45/90]_2s$, the size of which was $150 \times 100 \times 3.20$ mm³. The laminate was first coated with the epoxy-based adhesive by the blade coating method. The thickness of the adhesive was controlled by

the blade. Thereafter, the BP was laid on top of the adhesive and pressed by a steel plate (~70 g) to make the surface flat. The BP-coated laminate sample was cured in the oven following the recommended curing procedure [36]. The structure of the sample is schematically shown in Fig. 4. According to the structure of the samples, the compositions are denoted as “laminate-adhesive-surface film” in the sequence of bottom-up. The symbols “P”, “NEP”, “CEP”, “IEP” and “BP” are short for the pristine laminate, neat epoxy adhesive, conductive epoxy adhesive, insulating epoxy adhesive, and buckypaper, respectively. For example, “P-NEP” means laminate coated only by the neat epoxy adhesive, and “P-IEP-BP” represents laminate protected by insulating BN/EP adhesive and BP film.

Figure 4 A schematic diagram of the structure of the laminate samples coated with BP.

The lightning strike generator is shown in Fig. 5. This generator is capable of generating artificial lightning with waveform of 8/23 μ s (i.e. the time from 10% to 90% of the maximum current is 8 μ s, and the time from 10% to 50% through 90% of the maximum current is 23 μ s, Fig. 5b). For this study, artificial lightning with the peak current of 40 and 100 kA was utilized to inflict different states of damage to the samples as shown in Fig. 5b. Before simulated lightning strike tests, the sample was positioned with the BP side facing the artificial lightning, as shown in Fig. 5c. A copper pin was used as the discharge probe, the tip of which was laid just on the surface of the sample. The entire sample was supported at the two short ends between two copper electrodes. The sample was grounded along its perimeter to direct the current to the ground. Fig. 5d shows a typical photo of the sample after lightning strike. More detailed information can be found in [37].

Figure 5 Experimental setup and conditions for simulated lightning strike test: a) lightning strike generator, b) waveforms used in the test, c) close-up of the support fixture, d) typical image of the sample after strike.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 BP/TPU composites with enhanced mechanical properties

The neat TPU resin is thermoplastic rubber, namely, having low elastic modulus (~21 MPa), low failure strength (~33 MPa) and high ductility (elongation at break up to ~580%), as shown in the inset

of Fig. 6a. The as-prepared BP shows poor mechanical properties (Fig. 6a black line) with the elastic modulus of ~ 1.37 GPa, failure strength of ~ 11.58 MPa and elongation at break of $\sim 8\%$. After the introduction of TPU resin to BP, the mechanical properties of composite samples are found to be improved dramatically. At a proper TPU content, for example, in the case of sample BP/TPU-4, the best mechanical properties are obtained with elastic modulus of ~ 6 GPa, failure strength of ~ 123 MPa and toughness of ~ 36 MJ/m³, corresponding to ~ 3.4 -fold improvement in elastic modulus, ~ 9.6 -fold improvement in failure strength, and ~ 50 -fold improvement in toughness, compared to those of the as-prepared BP film. At very high resin fraction (e.g. BP/TPU-5), the mechanical properties decrease obviously, due to the excess TPU on sample surface.

The improvement can be attributed to the good MWCNTs-TPU interfacial adhesion and outstanding ductility of the TPU resin, which are confirmed by SEM images of the fracture surfaces and the in situ Raman measurement during tension, as discussed in our published paper [33].

Figure 6 Tensile curves (a) and key mechanical properties (b) of the neat TPU, as-prepared BP and BP/TPU composite samples

3.2 Tribological behavior of the BP/EP composites

Fig. 7 shows a typical curve of frictional coefficient (COF) vs. sliding time for the samples. At the initial sliding time (i.e., the running-in stage, as indicated in Fig. 7), the COF value tends to fluctuate significantly because the real contact area between the friction pairs increases gradually. Afterwards the COF value remains almost constant, especially for the BP/EP composites. In addition, the COF value of the neat epoxy sample shows periodic fluctuation in the steady stage, which is probably due to the separation of debris and transfer film from the surface of the ball.

Figure 7 Representative plots of friction coefficient vs. sliding time for the samples.

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the variation of COF and specific wear rate for the samples tested at various normal loads and sliding velocities. It is quite clear from Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 that both p- and f-BP/EP samples exhibit superior anti-wear performance compared to the neat epoxy samples in most cases, i.e., both of the COF values and specific wear rates are significantly decreased compared to those for the neat epoxy samples tested under the same wear conditions. Noteworthy, f-BP/EP samples show the best performance. For example, at a normal force of 6 N and sliding velocity of 20 mm/s, the COF value of the f-BP/EP composite is as low as 0.32, i.e. only 45% of that of the pure epoxy (0.71, Fig.

8b); and at a normal force of 2 N and sliding velocity of 120 mm/s, the specific wear rate of the f-BP/EP composite is as low as 19% of that of the neat epoxy sample (Fig. 9a).

Several possible mechanisms, including the enhanced mechanical properties, the self-lubricating effect of CNTs, the good fatigue resistance and the reduced adhesive wear of the BP/epoxy composite samples, as well as the developed continuous transfer films, are proposed to be responsible for the enhanced wear resistance, based on the tensile and nanoindentation results, Raman spectra and SEM worn surfaces of the friction pairs (refer to our published paper Ref.[35]).

Figure 8 Frictional coefficient of the samples tested under different conditions: a) and b) frictional coefficient vs. sliding velocity, c) and d) frictional coefficient vs. normal force.

Figure 9 Specific wear rate of the samples tested under different conditions: a) and b) wear rate vs. sliding velocity, c) and d) wear rate vs. normal force.

3.3 The application of BP in lightning strike protection of the CFRP laminates

After the pristine CFRP laminate samples (P-1) are subjected to lightning strike with peak current of 40 kA, carbon fiber breakage can be observed two or three layers deep from the surface at the lightning attachment point; at the same time, a strip-shaped ply-lift in the fiber direction, i.e. along the 45° direction, is found as shown in Fig. 10a₁. From the ultrasonic inspection images, damage near the lightning attachment point is also observed inside the laminate (Fig. 10a₃₋₄). The major causes for the fiber breakage are considered to be the shockwaves and the high resistive heat during the lightning strike. Moreover, as the current seeks for the shortest conductive path, i.e. the fiber direction, the damage of the outmost layer is also along the fiber direction (45°).

After simulated lightning strike test of 100 kA, the pristine CFRP laminate samples (P-2) are catastrophically destroyed. Besides the obvious fiber breakage and ply-lift, bulging and delamination around lightning attachment point are also observed as shown in Fig. 10b₁₋₂. The damaged area and depth of the samples struck at 100 kA (Fig. 10b_{3,4}) are much larger compared to those struck at 40 kA. When the laminates are subjected to harsh lightning strike tests, the ultra-high temperature may initiate the breakdown of the resin by pyrolysis. If the pyrolysis gases are trapped between the layers of the laminates, explosive release may occur with subsequent delamination.

Figure 10 Damage of the samples after lightning strike tests: a) P-1 struck at 40 kA, b), c) and d) are the characterization of the damage for P-2, P-NEP-2 and P-NEP-BP-3 struck at 100 kA, respectively.

The images labeled with subscripts 1, 2, 3 and 4 are the digital photographs of the overhead view, optical microscope image of the cross-sectional view, C-scope and B-scope images of the non-destructive inspection, respectively.

To verify the influence of the conductive BP (with electrical conductivity of 5.7×10^3 S/m) on the LSP effectiveness, samples coated with BP (P-NEP-BP-3) and without BP (P-NEP-2) were tested under 100 kA simulated lightning strike. The BP film was adhered onto the pristine laminate by ~ 500 μm thick EP adhesive in P-NEP-BP-3. As shown in Fig. 10c₁₋₂, the 500 μm thick EP adhesive coating in P-NEP-2 fails to protect the laminate from lightning strike; a strip-shaped ply-lift along 45°

direction is also observed. C-scope and B-scope images (Fig. 10c₃₋₄) also demonstrate this damage.

But for P-NEP-BP-3, the digital photograph (Fig. 10d₁) shows damage of the surface along the width direction in the middle of sample. C-scope image (Fig. 10d₃) also exhibits some dark sign along the width direction suggesting the presence of the defect due to the lightning strike. However, the cross-sectional view (Fig. 10d₂) and the B-scope image (Fig. 10d₄) indicate that the damage is mainly confined on the surface of the BP. Only small defect is found in the adhesive layer due to the high impact of the copper pin on the surface of the sample as shown in Fig. 10d₄. Because the current seeks for the shortest electrical path, i.e. the width direction, the damage of the BP is mainly along this direction, which is a typical feature of the well-protected sample coated with BP. These results suggest that conductive BP layer can promote the transfer of the electrical current to the ground, dissipate the energy and protect the laminate from damage.

In our research, we find that the conductivities and thickness of the adhesives also affect the LSP effectiveness. Generally speaking, conductive adhesive can further help to direct current, dissipate energy and contribute to the LSP effectiveness. So at the beginning of our research, the conductive CNTs/EP adhesive was chosen to enhance the LSP effectiveness. However, beyond our expectation, laminates coated by the conductive adhesive and BP (P-CEP-BP, Fig. 11a) is severely damaged even under gentle lightning strike test (40 kA). More specifically, both the coating and the outermost 45° fiber layer are destroyed by the lightning strike, which is similar with the pristine laminate (P-1, Fig. 10a). But samples coated with BP and neat adhesive (P-NEP-BP-1, Fig. 11b) or highly insulating adhesive (P-IEP-BP-1, Fig. 11c) only show tiny damage on the surface of the BP along the width direction and no damage is observed inside the CFRP laminates. Moreover, comparing Fig. 11b and Fig. 11c, it seems as if the damaged area of P-IEP-BP-1 is smaller than that of P-NEP-BP-1, implying that highly insulating BN/EP adhesive can perform better than the neat EP adhesive. According to all the above results, we can draw a short conclusion that insulating adhesives may be beneficial for LSP, while conductive adhesive may adversely affect the LSP effectiveness.

Figure 11 The influence of the adhesive conductivity on the LSP effectiveness: a), b) and c) are the characterization of P-CEP-BP, P-NEP-BP-1 and P-IEP-BP-1 after struck at 40 kA, respectively, the captions of the figures labeled with subscripts 1, 2, 3 and 4 are the same with those in Figure 10.

We also find that thicker insulating adhesives outperform thinner adhesives when coupled with the BP layer. To get an effective LSP and reduce the weight simultaneously, up to now, in our work, the best result is obtained by a coating composed of a 70 μm thick BP and a 200 μm thick BN/EP adhesive which can protect the CFRP laminate from lightning strikes at 100 kA. The total areal density of the BP and the BN/EP adhesive in this case is about 325 gsm. Compared to the commercial LSP products made of Cu screen (466 gsm) and Al screen (730 gsm), the weight reduction of the entire coating is $\sim 30\%$ and $\sim 55\%$, respectively.

The possible mechanisms are discussed according to the experimental results and finite element simulation. It is demonstrated that the conductive BP is essential to provide effective LSP by facilitating the electrical current to the ground; relatively thick insulating adhesive layer could hinder the transfer of the electricity through the thickness direction thus further enhance the LSP effectiveness; while conductive adhesive layer may promote the conduction of the current towards thickness direction and adversely affect the LSP effectiveness (Fig. 12). More information can be found in our paper [37].

Figure 12 Schematic of the possible LSP mechanisms for the CFRP laminate with different protective coatings: a) conductive adhesive or thin insulating adhesive layer coupled with BP; b) relatively thick insulating adhesive coupled with BP.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we prepared a relatively big BP with a diameter up to 285 mm through a solution filtration method, enhanced its mechanical properties (especially toughness) by a thermoplastic polyurethane elastomer and explored its potential application in tribology and lightning strike protection of the CFRP laminate. The following conclusions can be drawn:

(1) The ductile TPU was employed to enhance its mechanical properties. At a proper TPU volume fraction, the resultant composites gained simultaneous improvements in stiffness (3.4-fold), failure strength (9.6-fold) and toughness (51-fold) compared to those of the as-prepared BP film. The improvement can be attributed to the good MWCNTs-TPU interfacial adhesion and outstanding ductility of the TPU resin.

(2) BP was utilized to enhance the tribological properties of the epoxy resin. The CNTs were surface-modified by ozone in order to improve their interfacial adhesion with the matrix. Depending on the conditions of the wear tests, the frictional coefficient can be reduced from 0.71 for the neat resin down to 0.32 for ozone-modified BP/epoxy composite and the wear resistance can be improved by more than 4 times. Moreover, even after subjected to harsh wear, BP/epoxy composite still retained high electrical conductivity due to the robust CNTs network. Several possible mechanisms, including the enhanced mechanical properties, the self-lubricating effect of CNTs, the good fatigue resistance and the reduced adhesive wear of the BP/epoxy composite samples, as well as the developed continuous transfer films, were proposed to be responsible for the enhanced wear resistance.

(3) BP-based coatings composed of MWCNTs BP and insulating adhesives of the appropriate thickness were developed to protect the CFRP laminate from lightning strike. It was demonstrated that the conductive BP can facilitate the lightning current to the ground and dissipate the energy. Moreover, a relatively thick insulating adhesive, which outperformed the conductive adhesive, can hinder the transfer of the lightning current through the thickness direction to CFRP laminates, thus further enhance the LSP effectiveness. An optimized LSP coating was composed of a ~ 70 μm thick BP and a ~ 200 μm thick boron nitride modified epoxy insulating adhesive, which resulted in a weight reduction

up to 30% compared to the commercial Cu LSP coating, and could sustain the simulated lightning strike with peak current up to 100 kA.

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